

THE EFFECT OF THERMAL RESIDUAL STRESS FIELDS ON FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH IN Al/SiC_p METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of long-range thermal residual stresses on fatigue crack growth in an Al/SiC_p metal matrix composite has been examined. Stresses produced by quenching the material in plate form from high temperatures have been measured using neutron diffraction, and are seen to vary parabolically through the plate thickness, from compression at the surfaces to tension in the centre. These stresses have been shown to affect fatigue crack growth, either by producing bowed cracks, or causing acceleration of the crack growth rates as the crack progresses through the sample, depending on the crack front orientation relative to the residual stress field. This effect has been quantified by monitoring crack closure levels during fatigue, and by applying weight functions to determine the contribution of the residual stress field to the crack tip stress intensity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites have attracted increasing attention in recent years, due to their potential for weight savings in structural applications, by virtue of their increased specific strength and stiffness when compared to the unreinforced alloy matrices. Most commercial alloys are subjected to heat treatment to optimise their properties at some stage during the manufacturing process. For precipitation hardening aluminium alloys, a typical treatment would comprise solution treatment at around 500°C, quenching, and subsequent ageing. Some alloys e.g. 2124, are also particularly responsive to mechanical property enhancement by applying cold work between the solution heat treatment (SHT) and ageing¹.

Such thermal processing produces residual stresses within the material, due to the non-uniform temperature profiles within the bulk of the material which arise during rapid cooling. It is now well-established that mean microstresses (i.e. stresses that vary over small, sub-grain, distances) also develop during cooling within the matrix (tensile) and reinforcement (compressive) due to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion between the two phases²⁻⁴. However, the residual macrostress (long-range) fields produced by heat treatments are of more interest in the context of fatigue, as these are non-uniform and can vary considerably in magnitude across the thickness of the treated sample.

In this study we have examined the effect of water quenching an MMC plate on subsequent fatigue crack growth. The quench produces a through-thickness variation in residual stress, which is known

to have a marked effect on fatigue behaviour⁵. A largely one-dimensional stress variation is produced, due to cooling on the upper and lower plate surfaces, with biaxial stress states produced near the edges of the plate. This has been confirmed by photoelastic modelling using rapidly cooled araldite plate⁶. This contrasts with the effect produced if the material is heat treated as specimen blanks, where the stress field varies in two directions, due to cooling on four of the specimen faces. A fatigue crack grown in such a specimen will always exhibit crack front bowing, as the crack adopts a shape to give a constant ΔK across the crack front.

For material that has been heat treated as plate, a fatigue crack grown such that the crack front is parallel to the direction in which the residual stress field is varying would also exhibit such crack bowing effects. However, should the crack be grown with the crack front perpendicular to the direction of stress variation, then a straight crack front will be obtained, although the crack will experience varying values of residual stress as it progresses through the specimen. A straight crack front is required for valid interpretation of the fatigue data. Figure 1 shows the orientation of the standard edge-notched bend (SENB) specimens prepared relative to the parent plate to achieve this, and the labelling of axes used.

Figure 1: Axis labelling and specimen orientation

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Experiments have been performed on high-strength precipitation-hardening aluminium alloy composites, in the naturally aged (NA) and peak aged (PA) conditions. The composites were reinforced with 20 wt% F1200 (nominally 3 μm) grade particulate silicon carbide. The material was produced by BP Metal Composites Ltd, by a powder metallurgy route which comprises blending of the alloy powder and reinforcement, compaction, and consolidation by hot isostatic pressing. The billet was subsequently hot forged and rolled to a plate thickness of $\approx 15\text{mm}$.

The composite was subjected to an SHT for 2 hours, followed by a cold water quench. Neutron diffraction measurements were performed on two plates, designated 681/3 and A712A/4, in this condition. For fatigue samples, the material was aged to peak strength at 170°C for 5 hours, following the quench. This reduces the levels of residual stress within the composite: the compressive surface stress levels, as measured by hole drilling, have been seen to decrease from around 380 to 140 MPa⁷. Fatigue tests were carried out in the aged condition because it was found to be difficult to initiate and grow straight fatigue cracks in material subjected to natural ageing, due to the very high levels of compressive residual stress in the vicinity of the notch.

3. NEUTRON DIFFRACTION

Neutron diffraction experiments were performed at the ISIS facility of the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, U.K, and at the DR3 reactor at the Risø National Laboratory, Denmark. Measurements were made in order to determine the stresses within the composite plates introduced by the quench. The change in lattice plane spacing within the matrix or reinforcement produced by the quench stresses can be detected using Bragg diffraction. The changes in diffraction angle from a particular set of planes within sampling volumes along the z-axis allow the strains, and hence the stresses, to be determined through the thickness of the specimen⁸. Different strain directions are chosen by orienting the specimen relative to the incident and diffracted beams.

Fig. 2: Matrix strain recorded for plate A712A/4. Due to time constraints, strains were only measured from one surface to just beyond the midpoint, and the data points recorded have been reflected about the specimen centre for clarity. Curve fits are shown for two sets of peaks, to delineate the strain variation. Plate thickness = 15mm.

Measurements were made of the in-plane (*y*) and through-thickness (*z*) strains of two separate naturally-aged plates, as a function of position along the *z*-axis. Plate A712A/4 was tested using the pulsed neutron beam at ISIS, and the strains recorded for this plate are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3: Stress in the matrix of plate A712A/4 in *y* (in-plane) and *z* (through-thickness) directions, as a function of depth (*z*), deduced from the strains presented in Figure 2. When converting to stress, the matrix strain-free lattice parameter was chosen to give balance of the stresses across the specimen width (i.e. as if there were no thermal coefficient of expansion mismatch microstrain). Note how the in-plane and through-thickness strain variations combine to give approximately no stress variation in the through-thickness direction. Independent measurements on plate 681/3 are also shown, for which a strain-free lattice parameter was recorded.

The stresses calculated from this strain data are shown in Figure 3. No strain-free reference was recorded for this plate, and so, in calculating the stresses, stress balance has been assumed across the plate thickness. Effectively, this means that the microstresses arising from the mismatch in

coefficient of thermal expansion have been neglected. More detailed measurements were performed on plate 681/3, using the constant flux neutron source at Risø, and the results for this plate are also summarised in Figure 3. Given that a strain-free reference was measured in this case, these results confirm the use of the stress balance method.

It may be clearly discerned that the residual stress field within the plates varies as expected, from compressive surface stresses to tensile stresses within the centre of the samples. The variation is approximately parabolic, and similar results were obtained from simultaneous measurements of the reinforcement strains. The consistency in the results is particularly noteworthy, as comparable results have been obtained from two separate composite plates, using two different neutron spectrometers, one on a constant flux source and the other on a pulsed source. It should also be noted that, whilst a strain variation was observed in the through-thickness direction as a function of position along the z -axis, the stress in this direction is zero across the specimen width. This is as expected, given that the strain free lattice parameter was chosen so as to give stress balance, and this assumes that the mean matrix microstress is zero when analysing the data. However, as the through-thickness stress is constant across the width, this does indicate that the observed strains in the z -direction arise solely from Poisson's ratio effects. Future analysis of the data recorded for plate 681/3 will allow separation of the microstresses and macrostresses to be achieved.

Extrapolation of the measured stresses to the specimen surface suggests that compressive surface stresses in excess of 250 MPa were present. This is in line with measurements that have been made elsewhere^{7,9}.

4. CRACK CLOSURE MEASUREMENTS

Fatigue testing was performed on peak-aged SENB specimens with dimensions 12.5 x 12.5 x 100mm, cut from the plate as shown in Figure 1. Tests were performed under four point bending conditions, with a sinusoidal loading cycle at a frequency of 20 Hz. The crack length was monitored by a d.c. potential drop technique.

The effect of the thermal residual stress field on the stress intensity experienced at the tip of the fatigue crack was examined by measurements of crack closure levels. The thermal residual stresses have been shown, in these materials, to cause the crack growth rate to increase as the crack advances¹⁰, but it is not straightforward to evaluate the contribution of the residual stresses to this effect.

Crack closure levels were monitored by means of a strain gauge mounted on the back face of the specimen, opposite the notch. The crack opening stress intensity K_{op} is calculated from the point at which the load vs. relative strain plot for the loading half of the fatigue cycle changes slope, as the apparent compliance of the specimen changes and the crack begins to open. The effective stress intensity range at the crack tip is thus:

$$\Delta K_{eff} = K_{max} - K_{op} \quad (1)$$

K_{op} is comprised of two separate effects: K_{cl} , arising from the underlying closure mechanisms that operate in the material, typically roughness-induced; and K_{res} , which is the effect of the residual stresses present in the material. The underlying closure level may be determined by performing closure measurements on samples prepared from material that has been subjected to plastic straining following the heat treatment, as this has been shown, by observing the degree of crack front bowing, to relieve the macro residual stress variation in the material.

Figure 4 shows closure measurements performed on specimens of the composite material in the peak-aged condition. One specimen was machined from plate which had been stretched following heat treatment. The applied stress intensity was reduced as the crack progressed through the samples.

The data obtained from the stretched material indicate that there is little or no dependence on ΔK of the inherent closure mechanisms for the material over the stress intensity range measured, as the closure level is relatively constant at around 2.3 to 2.6 MPa \sqrt{m} .

For the material containing a thermal residual stress field, the closure levels are seen to undergo a marked reduction as the crack increases in length, decreasing from 3.3 to 2.7 MPa \sqrt{m} as the crack grows from $a/W=0.36$ to $a/W=0.5$. It is unfortunate that, when performing tests on small specimens, crack growth beyond $a/W=0.6$ is not feasible due to the large specimen compliance at such crack lengths. This is potentially the most interesting region in which to monitor the residual stress effects, as the closure levels could become progressively more tensile or compressive, depending on the way in which the residual stress field relaxes and redistributes as the crack length increases.

Figure 4: Crack closure vs. crack position in PA material

5. MODELLING OF RESIDUAL STRESS EFFECTS

Some simple modelling has been applied to the interaction of the residual stress field with the fatigue crack, to determine the usefulness and accuracy of these models in predicting the effect of such stress fields on fatigue crack growth. The results from the models may be directly compared to the experimental measurements.

One common method for evaluating the effect of a stress field on the stress intensity experienced at a crack tip is the use of weight functions. Weight functions are produced by mathematical derivation of the crack tip stress intensity for the sample geometry (from, for example, Westergaard's method¹¹), and superposition of the residual stress field onto the crack tip geometry¹². However, other methods, such as analytical fits to finite element models, are also available¹³.

The residual stress field for the problem in question is combined with the weight function to produce an absolute value of K_{res} at a particular crack length. It is calculated as:

$$K_{res}(a) = \int_0^a \sigma_y^{res}(z) m(z,a) dz \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_y^{res}(z)$ is the in-plane residual stress field in the material (i.e. that which will contribute to crack opening); a is the length of the crack; and $m(z,a)$ is the weight function for a given specimen geometry. For the SENB specimens used¹⁴:

$$m(z,a) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi a}} \cdot \frac{G\left(\frac{z}{a}, \frac{a}{W}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{a}{W}\right)^{3/2} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{z}{a}\right)^2}} \quad (3)$$

where W is the width of the specimen.

$G(z/a, a/W)$ is a polynomial function of the crack length a/W , and the position of the sampling point from the crack tip, z/a . As it is detailed elsewhere¹⁴, it is not reproduced here.

When applied to a parabolic residual stress field of the form measured (Figure 3), scaled to give a surface stress of -140MPa (as measured in the PA material⁷), K_{res} is seen to behave as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: K_{res} vs. crack length for a parabolic residual stress field in a PA SENB specimen

This method neglects any effect of the mean phase microstresses within the material, assuming that only the long-range macrostresses will have a significant effect on the fatigue behaviour. This would appear to be reasonable, as the matrix and reinforcement microstresses are short-range stresses, and therefore they would be expected to have little effect on the crack opening.

In the region of crack lengths over which the closure measurements were made (a/W from 0.36 to 0.5), the predicted K_{res} values decrease from -5.3 to -3.7 MPa√m. This change is of the same order as the decrease in K_{op} as measured by crack closure levels, being approximately 50% higher than those measured directly, even without attempting to account for the fundamental closure mechanisms that operate within the material. This may arise because the weight function technique does not account for any change in the form of the residual stress field as the crack advances¹⁵. The stress field that is imposed upon the cracked sample is taken to be unchanged relative to that which existed in the unnotched specimen blank as cut from the heat treated plate.

It seems highly unlikely that this is an accurate description. As the crack grows, the local stresses will be relieved, and a bending stress must be superimposed upon the residual stress field in order to ensure that all moments are balanced. This has been modelled separately simply by considering the specimen as consisting of a series of linked rods, and completely relaxing the stress in each rod as the crack grows through it. It is found that the subsequent bending stress required for moment

balance acts to produce compressive stresses ahead of the crack for all crack lengths. If this is so, no tensile residual stresses would be sampled, contrary to that indicated using the weight function technique, for crack lengths greater than $a/W=0.7$. In reality, it is more plausible that some combination of these two extremes operates. The stresses will relax only in the vicinity of the crack, not in the far field. However, although large-scale relaxation would not be expected where fatigue crack face touching can occur, the weight function technique does not account for the presence of the initiator notch, which will certainly have a marked effect on the residual stress field that is present and acting on the crack.

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. The thermal residual stress field arising from quenching of a plate has been measured by neutron diffraction in an SiC-particulate-reinforced aluminium alloy. The stress field showed the expected parabolic variation from compression at the sample surfaces to tension in the centre of the plate, with surface stresses of over 250 MPa in the as-quenched condition.
2. The effect of such a thermal residual stress field on long fatigue crack growth in these materials has been examined. Measurements of crack closure levels as a function of crack length have been made, and are seen to decrease from 3.3 to 2.7 MPa \sqrt{m} between $a/W = 0.36$ to 0.5. This is a result of the effects of the residual stresses. Tests performed on stretched plate, in which the stresses have been relieved, show no dependence of closure level on crack length.
3. The contribution of the thermal residual stress field to the stress intensity at the crack tip has been evaluated by weight function modelling. The results approximate to those obtained experimentally, varying from -5.3 to -3.7 MPa \sqrt{m} over the same range of crack lengths as the closure measurements. These values may be higher than those measured experimentally because of the failure of the model to account for the presence of the initiator notch in the specimen, or due to relaxation and redistribution of the residual stress field during cracking.

In future work, neutron diffraction experiments will be performed on fatigue cracked specimens containing residual stress fields to reveal how the stress field is altered by the presence of the crack, and how the stresses redistribute ahead of and behind the crack as it advances. This will allow us to evaluate the applicability of weight function modelling techniques to residual stress situations.

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